

DAMAGE TESTING OF CROSSPLY LAMINATES UNDER HIGH STRAIN RATES. EFFECTS OF INTRALAMINAR SHEAR STRESSES.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an investigation on the characterization of an energy absorption phenomenon existing during a collision between composite structures : it concerned intralaminar shear loading at fibre-matrix interface, preponderant in the degradation of long fibres reinforced composite materials under impact. An uniaxial tensile test on symmetrical $(\pm 45^\circ)_s$ glass/epoxy crossply laminates, adapted to impact apparatus, is presented. Then, we modified two impact testing devices to damage samples : a servo-hydraulic testing machine and a Hopkinson bars tensile apparatus. Finally, logarithmic evolution laws of damage threshold due to intralaminar shear stresses are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Energy absorption phenomena, produced by cars collisions or crashes, require a particular investigation. Intralaminar shear stresses at fibre-matrix interface seem to be one of the preponderant mechanisms governing the degradation of long fibres reinforced composite structures, as it has been proved during composite tube compression tests [1].

An uniaxial tensile test on symmetrical $(\pm 45^\circ)_s$ E glass/epoxy crossply laminates is presented; this technique generates a preponderant intralaminar shear loading within each ply of the laminate.

We have adapted this method to failure impact tests; we use an impact apparatus with a large inertia wheel loading and a high velocity servo-hydraulic testing machine. Strain rates produced with these apparatus vary between 10 to 10^3 s^{-1} . In this way, we particularly try to show high strain rate effects which appear a determining factor on material intralaminar shear behaviour.

Furthermore, damage phenomena appear to have a great role on the behaviour of the material, so we have decided to conduct our study using damage mechanics. Therefore, in addition with the servo-hydraulic testing machine, we modified a Hopkinson bars tensile apparatus to damage samples at different known and reproducible stresses. The aims of this approach are to evaluate the effects of high strain rates on the damage threshold due to shear stresses.

I. UNIAXIAL TENSILE TEST ON $(\pm 45^\circ)_s$ LAMINATES.

We define a loading test as creating, within long fibre composites, an intralaminar shear stress state. According to P. H. PETIT [2], we propose a simple test, inexpensive and which gives a stress state similar to those of the reference torsion test. It consists to load symmetrical $(\pm 45^\circ)_s$ crossply laminates in uniaxial tension [3]. This technique generates a preponderant intralaminar shear loading within each ply of the laminate.

Based on the classical laminate theory, intralaminar shear stresses and strains are deduced from the stress-strain behaviour curve of the laminate measured under tension and using the mechanical properties of a simple unidirectional ply. The intralaminar shear strain component within

a considered ply, γ_{12} , is expressed as a function of the whole specimen longitudinal (ϵ_x) and transverse (ϵ_y) strain components : $\gamma_{12} = (\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y)$ (1)

The tangential intralaminar shear modulus, G_{12} , within each ply, is written :

$$G_{12} = \frac{2 U_1 E_{xx}}{8 U_1 - E_{xx}} \quad (2) \quad \text{where} \quad U_1 = \frac{(E_{11} + E_{22} + 2 \nu_{21} E_{11})}{8 (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})} \quad (3)$$

E_{xx} : specimen longitudinal modulus (from stress σ_x - strain ϵ_x curve); E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , ν_{21} : material longitudinal, transverse stiffnesses and Poisson's ratios measured with an unidirectional ply.

The corresponding intralaminar shear stress component is : $\tau_{12} = G_{12} \gamma_{12}$ (4)

An other approach of this laminate theory, proposed by W. ROSEN [4], allows us to simplify the determination of intralaminar shear stress and strain components, in only requiring the loading stress and the specimen longitudinal and transverse strains :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tau_{12} = \frac{\sigma_x}{2} \\ \gamma_{12} = (\epsilon_x - \epsilon_y) \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

II. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES.

In this second part, we adapt this method to four testing devices. First, an INSTRON statical tensile machine is used to achieve each future low speed tests.

Then, a tensile testing machine with a large inertia wheel loading allows us to test composites until failure under high strain rates (10^2 to 10^3 s⁻¹). The principle of this apparatus is based on a large inertia wheel ($m = 617$ kg), with a constant rotational speed (5 to 50 rad.s⁻¹), which catches the head of the specimen (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Principle of the tensile testing machine with a large inertia wheel loading.

A piezoelectric quartz force transducer and a ZIMMER electro-optical extensometer, adjusted to the sample, give measurements, respectively, of load and longitudinal displacement.

To develop our study under medium strain rates (10 to 10^2 s⁻¹), the same failure tests are achieved with an INSTRON high velocity servo-hydraulic testing machine. This apparatus consists of giving a constant velocity to an hydraulic jack. Its acceleration is progressive and it reaches its maximum speed after a fixed displacement; in this way, the hydraulic jack is accelerated in neutral and movement is then transmitted to the specimen after contact with a block sliding along a cylindrical guide (Figures 2).

To achieve damage tests under high strain rates, two apparatus, after some improvements, are used. The first one is based on the use of the servo-hydraulic testing machine and allows us to test samples under medium strain rates (10 to 10^2 s⁻¹).

However, the principle of the servo-hydraulic machine doesn't allow us to stop the hydraulic jack displacement during test. In this way, the sample under tension fails before the end of the test. To avoid this failure, held in succession with composite material to damage, a mechanical fuse is fixed (Figure 2 and 3). Failure of this fuse allows us to stop the test; composite material is therefore damaged but not failed.

Figure 2. Servo-hydraulic testing machine with PMMA fuse.

Figure 3. Loading system with PMMA fuse.

PMMA (Poly-methyl-metacrylate) has been chosen as the mechanical fuse because of its brittle behaviour and since it is easily machinable. Under DEN (Double Edge Notched) samples, PMMA failure strength, at each chosen load level (function of lengths notches), is precise and reproducible. Therefore, at the same strain rate, we damage, using servo-hydraulic machine, ($\pm 45^\circ$)_s composite lamina at different known stress levels.

Figure 4. Impact Hopkinson bars apparatus.

At the highest strain rates (until 10^3 s^{-1}), we use a modified Hopkinson bars tensile apparatus (Figure 4). This mechanism is made up of two long cylindrical steel bars (input and output bars) and the sample is held between them. A projectile, propelled by a compressed air gun along the input bar, crashes an anvil attached to the free end of this very bar. A tensile longitudinal elastic wave is then created and spreads towards the sample and the output bar. A transmission-reflection phenomenon appears at the input bar / sample and sample / output bar interfaces. A tensile wave, transmitted within the sample and the output bar, is entirely reflected as a compressive wave at the free end of this one. We can note that the tensile wave previously reflected at the input bar / sample interface has become compressive.

Analysis of results obtained during tests are obtained using the elastic waves propagation theory. Strain gages, connected in full Wheatstone's bridge, are pasted on each bar. A pre-established load calibration allows us to deduce the stresses and strains in sample. Then, a computer reduces all the data.

We improved the Hopkinson apparatus to damage samples at different known and reproducible stresses, without nevertheless breaking them. Hence, at the same projectile impact rate, we use projectiles of different lengths, since the duration of the wave created within the input bar is proportional to these lengths ($T = 2L / c$ where T , L and c are respectively signal duration, length of

the projectile and the celerity of a wave within this element). The reflected and transmitted waves within the input and output bars, respectively, are trapped to avoid the wave to return within the sample by reflection at the free end of each bar. Like this, we can control the damage within the material.

For this purpose, we have added a new bar with same cylindrical geometry in contact with the free end of the input bar (Figure 6). The reflected wave at the input bar / sample interface, became compressive, is fully transmitted within this trapping-bar and a loss of contact between each element traps the signal.

Figure 6. Trapping systems : (a) in the input bar and (b) in the output bar.

In a similar manner, the transmitted tensile wave within the output bar is trapped by a tube sliding along this bar. The trapping-tube, after loss of contact with the output bar, is stopped by a dissipative energy system external to the Hopkinson bars apparatus. The contact between the trapping-tube and the output bar, before test, is ensured by an anvil attached to the preceding free end of the bar (Figure 6).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The material used to test was a symmetrical ($\pm 45^\circ$) crossply laminate constituted with E glass long fibres embedded in an epoxy matrix (STRUCTIL). Fibre content is 60% wt. Samples are machined, from composite plates and with a water jet cutting system, to (12.5 ± 0.1) mm long, (5.7 ± 0.1) mm wide and (2.3 ± 0.1) mm thick dumbbell shape specimens.

III. 1. Failure tests.

Uniaxial tensile preliminary tests were achieved on crossply laminates with an INSTRON static testing machine. Figure 7 presents a typical load versus time curve obtained during a test at a constant 0.0083 s^{-1} strain rate. The strain versus time curve is linear and the composite behaviour is visualized with this graph.

Figure 7. Load versus time curve under 0.0083 s^{-1} strain rate.

Figure 8. Failure strengths and yield stresses versus strain rates.

The load versus time curve shows a non linear behaviour during a first loading stage. Then, a quasi linear pseudo plastic stage appears with increasing load until sudden failure of the sample. The first linear stage is elastic as we will prove later. From this load versus time curve, two characteristic parameters of the intralaminar shear are measured. The first is the failure strength, which issue from the failure load. The second is the yield stress. To measure it, we consider that the yield limit appears at the behaviour change between non linear and linear stages.

Failure and yield mean values, from 0.0083 to 0.17 s⁻¹ strain rates, are plotted in figure 8. Each parameter increases, versus strain rates, in a logarithmic law.

High strain rates tests (10 to 10³ s⁻¹), achieved using tensile machine with inertia wheel loading (Figure 9) and servo-hydraulic apparatus (Figure 10), show again two stages in the composite behaviour. Response is, first, quasi linear. Then, as slope changes, a pseudo plastic stage appears with increasing load until failure of the sample.

Figure 9. Load versus time curve under 415 s⁻¹ strain rate.

Figure 10. Load versus time curve under 4.8 s⁻¹ strain rate.

- Static failure strengths (MPa)
- Static yield stresses (MPa)
- ▲ Failure strengths under medium strain rates (MPa)
- ▲ Yield stresses under medium strain rates (MPa)
- Failure strengths under high strain rates (MPa)
- Yield stresses under high strain rates (MPa)

Figure 11. Failure strengths and yield stresses versus strain rates.

Moreover, the plot of failure strengths and yield stresses versus high strain rates (Figure 11) allows us to say that the previous static logarithmic laws agree with dynamic tests.

Finally, a broken specimen, during a dynamic tensile test (Figure 12), is shown on figure . We observe a typically intralaminar shear failure within each ply of the laminate.

Figure 12. Broken specimen under 247 s⁻¹ strain rate.

III. 2 Damage tests.

Loading-unloading tests were achieved with the INSTRON static testing machine under 0.0083 and 0.042 s⁻¹ strain rates. Uniaxial stress versus time and longitudinal strain curves, under 0.0083 s⁻¹ strain rate, are plotted, respectively, on figures 13 and 14.

Figure 13. Uniaxial stress versus time curve under 0.0083 s⁻¹ strain rate.

Figure 14. Uniaxial stress versus displacement curve under 0.0083 s⁻¹ strain rate.

A damage normalized parameter D is defined from a measurement of the stress versus time slope evolution related to each loading cycle. So, $D_i = (p_i - p_{i+1}) / p_i$ where p_i is the slope of the stress versus time curve measured during the number i loading. In this way, the measurement of the number $(i+1)$ slope gives a value of damage parameter D_i , related to the material submitted to the number i loading.

This damage parameter D relates damage level due to intralaminar shear loading within composite materials. In fact, damage indicator is, by slope measurement of the stress versus time curve which corresponds to the longitudinal modulus, the intralaminar shear modulus (see equation (2)).

Figure 15. Static damage curve under 0.0083 and 0.042 strain rates.

On figure 15, the damage parameter D_i is plotted versus stresses from two tests achieved under 0.0083 and 0.042 s⁻¹ strain rates. It appears that damage initiation within the material is influenced by strain rates : a strain rate increase delays the initiation of the damage within crossply laminates under intralaminar shear loading. On the other hand, during the first non linear behaviour stage ($\sigma < 80$ MPa), composite is not damaged ($D < 0.06$). Loading-unloading curves show a reverse behaviour during this first stage; the behaviour is therefore elastic.

Damage tests under medium strain rates were achieved with servo-hydraulic machine under 4.8, 20.9 and 80 s⁻¹ strain rates.

Damage levels within each composites are then measured. In this way, a second static tensile test ($V = 10$ mm/min) is achieved with each of these damaged samples. The aim is to measure longitudinal modulus which is a damage indicator. Using an extensometer to the exact longitudinal

strain measurements, we measure statical longitudinal modulus, at 0.2% strain, on each damaged specimen.

Longitudinal modulus of undamaged samples were measured and became references to compute damage parameter D :

$$D = \frac{E_0 - E_D}{E_0} \quad (6) \quad \text{where } D \text{ is damage parameter,}$$

E_0 and E_D are, respectively, longitudinal modulus of the undamaged and damaged specimens.

This damage parameter, related to the longitudinal modulus and therefore to the intralaminar shear modulus, is a representative value of the damage due to intralaminar shear loading.

When subjected to a 4.8 s⁻¹ strain rate test, this damage parameter D increases as shown in figure 16. Measurements of the damage initiation threshold versus low and medium strain rates are achieved and plotted in figure 17. Furthermore, the damage rate of increase ($\partial D / \partial \sigma$) versus strain rates is plotted in figure 18. Finally, a second damage threshold which is related to the material failure is measured and data are listed in table 1.

Figure 16. Damage parameter versus impact loading, under 4.8 s⁻¹ strain rate.

Strain rates (s ⁻¹)	D* (damage threshold at failure material)
0.0083	0.44
0.042	0.34
4.8	0.49
20.9	0.21
80	0.39

Table 1. Damage threshold at the failure material versus strain rates.

Figure 17. Damage initiation threshold versus strain rates.

Figure 18. Damage rate of increase versus strain rates.

The damage initiation threshold increases with strain rates in a logarithmic law (Figure 17). On the other side, the damage rate of increase ($\partial D / \partial \sigma$), which is a damage propagation rate indicator, decreases with increasing strain rate in a new logarithmic law (Figure 18). Finally, damage at the material failure isn't subject to a particular law. Therefore, we compute an average value which is valid under low and medium strain rates : $D^* = 0.36$.

Another tensile apparatus is used to damage composites under higher strain rates (10² to 10³ s⁻¹). As we explained before we modified a Hopkinson bars tensile apparatus because waves returning to each free end of the bar have to be avoided so not as to damage composites twice. For

this reason, a particular attention has been given to create these two wave trapping systems at the input and output bars.

We tested the input bar trapping system during a test without the sample between the input and output bars; at this new input bar free end, the incident tensile wave was entirely reflected in a compressive wave. We trapped this new compressive wave and the results we obtained came from the figure 19 curve analysis.

Figure 19. Trapped wave in input bar.

Figure 20. Trapped wave in output bar.

We can note, first, that stress intensity strongly decreased when the trapping system works and the new no-trapped signal becomes a tensile wave. But, it is more important to compare decreasing energies before and after they have been trapped. In this case, the new reflected wave (not trapped) is very weak, proving efficiency of this device.

Relative results of the output bar trapping system show, again, a great decrease in the energy of the wave to trap and make us to consider these values as satisfying (Figure 20).

These different results are proved to be correct and allow us to continue, under the highest strain rates, our damage studies on composite materials under intralaminar shear loading.

CONCLUSIONS.

We have clearly shown that mechanical parameters related to intralaminar shear loading increase in a logarithmic law with low, medium and high strain rates.

Furthermore, study of the damage processes allows us to say that damage initiation in composite materials under intralaminar shear loading increases with low and medium strain rates although the damage propagation rate decreases when this last parameter grows.

Actually, damage processes have not been studied under the highest strain rates (10^2 to 10^3 s⁻¹). Therefore, our aims are to elaborate a valid damage evolution law under these high strain rates.

Finally, a micro-mechanical analysis will allow us to localise microcracks within each ply of the laminate. X-ray radiographs and scanning electron micrographs will be used to understand microcracking processes.

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